

Garvan Institute
of Medical Research

Garvan's love-hate relationship with commercial clouds

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Project Goal

Five years ago the Garvan Institute of Medical Research embraced genomics to underpin all its research, and thereby became Australia's biggest genome data producer. It was never going to be possible to meet Garvan's aspirational goals using the institute's on-premises computing infrastructure (currently 5000 compute cores and fast Petabyte storage). Today, Garvan computes and runs services on all commercial clouds (AWS, Azure and Google). Here we report back to the ARDC in these areas:

1. How Garvan currently manages costs on commercial clouds and providers of Platforms as a Service (PaaS), specifically [DNAnexus](#).
2. How Garvan decides between commercial and on-premise solutions and our advice to the ARDC.
3. How the ARDC could be a valuable partner to research organisations in supporting this demand.

Approach

Garvan has annual commercial cloud expenses that exceed \$1million. This computation is in addition to its on-premise 5000 CPU core computer farm and multi-petabyte storage. Garvan is continually evolving its thinking on driving down the costs of computation and data storage without compromising on its research goals, and the return of investment from its genomics data.

In this report we have shared with the ARDC our experiences, and evolving thinking in the area of the three questions we have asked (above), and how the ARDC could realise the vision articulated in its name and become Australia's Data Commons.

Garvan's usage of commercial clouds is both in the form of using native cloud functionality, ie. as direct customers of Amazon Web Services (AWS), Microsoft Azure and Google. It also is a customer of DNAnexus, a Californian company that offers its genome analysis and storage solutions on both AWS and Azure. Garvan's usage of these clouds and DNAnexus are as follows:

1. Running production (whole genome) workflows on all commercial clouds.
2. Running production workflows on DNAnexus

3. Sharing of data with collaborators through DNAnexus
4. Running Garvan's Vectis Genome Analysis Platform that include components running in a hybrid mode that includes on-premise, Google Cloud and AWS.

Here we report on our experiences of running these four services and how our thinking has evolved.

Garvan's usage of Commercial Clouds

The Broad Institute's [best practice whole genome analysis](#) pipeline comprising BWA-MEM and GATK was dockerised for running on both AWS and Microsoft Azure (Figure 1). Simple batching of the jobs was done with AWS native tools, whereas a Grid Engine cluster was instantiated on Azure using Microsoft's Cycle Cloud.

Figure 1. Deployment of whole genome workflow onto multiple infrastructures. From a single source repository the Broad Institute's best practice BWA-MEM/GATK was deployed to run as Docker containers on AWS and Azure. The code ran at Garvan in a Singularity container and this was also the source of the custom solution built to run on the NCI.

Garvan's usage of DNAnexus

DNAnexus provides a Platform as a Service (PAAS) for the genomics community. The DNAnexus solution is available on both Amazon Web Services (AWS) and Microsoft's Azure clouds. Obvious advantages of the offering is that DNAnexus provides a feature-rich environment for the running of genome analyses and the storage and sharing of data. The environment supports both web-based user interface as well as a rich Application Programming Interface (API) to support the scripting of complete workflows that may involve the uploading of data to the platform, running an analysis, and sharing the results with collaborators or partners. Built on the infrastructure of commercial clouds the DNAnexus platform is truly scalable in terms of both computational resources and data storage. It also offers object storage (S3) as well as the option of archiving data (glacier on AWS) in order to reduce costs further.

Findings

According to cloud leaders eg. Peter Norvig, head of Google research, the simple idea of cloud is for businesses to sell their services at a price that leaves a profit once cloud-costs have been deducted. It has also been clear that startup companies needing to grow their businesses very rapidly embrace cloud as the cloud infrastructure never constrains their needs to scale. Both of these scenarios make sense in commercial settings, but at Garvan we have found it difficult to use these same paradigms for our research computational needs. In summary *we found that everything we needed to do from a computational, storage, or sharing perspective could be done in the cloud - if we could come up with the economic model to pay for our utilisation*. We were mostly unsuccessful in doing so, but during our time working in this area we identified, or were able to confirm, the following lessons of cloud:

- Computing around the clock (24/7) on cloud is never cost-effective.
- The cost of using 1 cpu for 100 hours or 100 cpus for one hour is the same thing for a cloud and provides great opportunities for scaling in terms of actual throughput. Cloud performance is in our experience about half of our on-premise solutions.
- Data destroys almost all the advantages of cheap cloud usage. Mainly because of cloud egress costs.

We found flexibility by the cloud provider to dramatically change the rules eg. waiving egress costs in some cases to increase the complexity of reaching an understanding around cloud economics. However, we finally came up with the following solution:

- The only advantage of using cloud in a cost-effective way is to reduce the egress costs. Intermediate large files in genome workflows need to be deleted to make this option viable (Figure 2).
- Data sharing should be supported in-house.

Figure 2. Optimal Cloud Genome Workflow. Sequence reads generated at Garvan are copied to the NCI to serve as a long-term backup and also uploaded to the cloud. In the cloud a best practices GATK workflow is run. Sequence reads and mapped files (red rectangle) are deleted. Only the 6 Gigabyte variant files are downloaded. Thereby effectively eliminating 97.5% of the egress costs.

Analysis, or emerging themes

Cloud is particularly good at supporting analyses at scale. It is also becoming increasingly richer in its offerings. For example our group at Garvan were early adopters of MapD (now [OmniSci](#)), an open source SQL database that runs on General Purpose Graphical Processing Units (GPGPUs). MapD forms part of Garvan's Vectis genome analysis platform that supports the [Sydney Genomics Collaborative](#) and as [Variant Atlas](#) for the Australian Genomics Health Alliance. At the time we did not have the required GPGPU cards to run the database and used it in the cloud. While performance was excellent we still saw benefits in using a caching server, and opted for [Redis](#) that we were able to deploy in multiple cloud regions across the world. In doing so all previously asked queries were handled by the caching server rather than MapD. This example highlights how we risk "missing out" by not being in the cloud. Yet, this type of thinking remains dependent on the ability to "drive more value" out of the data. In 2016 Garvan spun out a commercial company that provided WGS as a pathology test. In this scenario - this type of thinking made sense, however, Garvan has yet to find a way to do this for research. Part of the Vectis platform also includes a scale-out Apache Kudu database. Developed by [Cloudera](#), the highly responsive Kudu services need to persist and cannot be instantiated on demand. In personal communication with Cloudera they have no customers anywhere in the world that run their Kudu services on the cloud because of the prohibitive costs of persisting these services on a cloud infrastructure. At Garvan we do the same and this has led to a hybrid design for our Vectis services where our Kudu cluster runs on premise, while MapD and other frontend services are on AWS and Google cloud respectively.

Data Sharing

DNAexus provides excellent opportunities for sharing genomics data via the convenience of the command line or API. However, at the scale at which Garvan generates and shares data this service costs \$100,000 per annum. Garvan opted to provide this functionality in-house. The benefit of sharing large genomics datasets over the web means that the size of storage is more important than its performance, and Garvan's solution using the [filesender](#) protocol as used by AARNet works well.

Final Comments

Lastly, a more disconcerting trend appears to be the insatiable appetite that cloud providers have for hiring engineers. From our perspective, we appear to provide outstanding training and experience for engineers whose skills and experience are then very attractive to cloud providers. Therefore, we may eventually need to fully embrace cloud - not because it's necessarily better, but because we're no longer able to support our local services because of staff challenges.

Opportunities for the Australian Research Data Commons.

Using the hybrid computing approach described in Figure 3 we believe the ARDC could provide extraordinary opportunities to highly interconnected ecosystems such as that of Garvan, the NCI and commercial clouds. Production workflows are not inherently valuable. Instead, it is the results generated by these workflows that have real value. Investments by the ARDC into the storing of datasets at eg. the NCI could support an important aspect of the vision of a Data Commons - the creation of an economy around data. The principle that not all datasets and services are created equal should apply. So a dataset that is never used has limited or no value to the ARDC and all costs should be passed on to the user. In contrast a popular, regularly accessed dataset or service is valuable to the ARDC (in terms of utility) as well as the researcher. In these cases, it would make sense for the ARDC to share some or all of the costs with the researcher, and support expert groups to build software solutions for unlocking the value of the data.

Australian Research Data Commons

Figure 3. An ARDC interconnected ecosystem. The ARDC could support the creation or storage of datasets of tangible value at eg. the NCI. Expert groups such as Garvan’s Data Sciences Platform would drive value from these data using diverse computing approaches with both Garvan and the NCI having fast connections (direct connects) to commercial clouds. Cloud usage would be primarily to support the bursting of increased data processing needs. To eliminate egress costs all input and intermediate files deleted on the cloud and only results returned.

Issues and Barriers to Goals

No issues or barriers were identified. Overall Garvan spent \$300,000 running these analyses and workflows in the last 4 months.